

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF A NOVEL EPOXY RESIN - N, N-DIGLYCIDYL-FURFURLAMINE

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SUMMARY

A novel epoxy resin with thermally remendability was successfully synthesized through a two-step reaction between 2-furfurylamine and epichlorohydrin. The molecular structure and thermal reversibility of the resin were demonstrated. Having been cured, the resin was characterized by low viscosity, high healing efficiency, and similar mechanical properties as conventional epoxy.

Keywords: Epoxy resin, thermal reversibility, healing performance

INTRODUCTION

Appearance of internal microcracks is a fatal problem for polymers and polymer composites utilized as structural components. Development and coalescence of the cracks would cause catastrophic failure. Therefore, imparting self-healing function to the materials is an ideal way for prolonging their lifetimes.

Self-repairing polymers and polymer composites have attracted increasing research interests [1]. Substantial achievements have been made in this field, which can roughly be classified into two strategies [2]: (i) intrinsic self-healing - polymers are able to heal cracks by themselves without the aid of any healing agent, and (ii) extrinsic self-healing - healing agent is pre-embedded in the matrix. For the latter, the matrix resin itself is not a healable one. Healing agent has to be encapsulated and embedded into the materials in advance. As soon as the cracks destroy the fragile capsules, the healing agent would be released into the crack planes due to capillary effect. Then, the cracks are autonomously re-bonded as a result of polymerization of the released healant [3-8].

The so-called intrinsic self-healing polymers and polymer composites are based on specific performance of the polymers and polymeric matrices that enables crack healing under certain stimulation (mostly heating). Autonomic healing without external intervention is not available in these materials for the time being. The works by Chen et al. represent the pilot exploration in this direction [9]. They synthesized highly cross-linked polymeric materials with multi-furan and multi-maleimide via Diels-Alder reaction. At temperatures above 120°C, the "intermonomer" linkages disconnect but then reconnect upon cooling. This process is fully reversible and can be used to restore fractured parts of the polymers. In principle, an infinite number of crack healing is available without the aid of additional catalysts, monomers and special surface treatment.

Because of its excellent properties, epoxy has found wide applications in industries as surface coatings, structural adhesives, printed circuit boards, insulation materials for electronic devices, and advanced composites matrices. Nevertheless, curing reactions of epoxy with its hardeners are generally irreversible, so that cured epoxy can hardly exhibit crack remendability as a result of lack of the ability of recombination of broken molecules. In this context, it would be a reasonable starting point to develop self-healing epoxy materials.

To endow epoxy resin with remendability, we synthesized a novel epoxy resin, N, N-diglycidyl-furfurylamine (DGFA), to combine epoxide with furan groups in one molecule. The epoxide groups can react with traditional curing agent like anhydride to form an epoxy network, providing the material with outstanding mechanical properties and thermal resistance as usual. Meanwhile, the furan groups can react with maleimide to introduce thermally reversible Diels-Alder (DA) bonds into the epoxy network. Eventually, the molecular networks in the cured material are comprised of two types of intermonomer linkage. Advantages of epoxy and intrinsic reworkable ability join together. In addition, the synthetic approach is relatively simple.

Since the cured epoxy network consists of two kinds of chemical bonds (i.e. thermally stable crosslinking bonds owing to the reaction of epoxide groups with curing agent, and thermally reversible Diels-Alder bonds), its thermal reversibility can be realized below glass transition temperature. Thereby, cracks in the cured epoxy are mended while keeping integrity of the material. Furthermore, by adjusting the proportions of the thermally stable bonds and thermally reversible bonds, healing performance of the new epoxy can be easily controlled. This paper discussed synthesis and characterization of DGFA resin and the related curing behaviour. Thermal reversibility and remendability of the resultant were also examined for having a deeper understanding of the structure-property relationship.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Synthesis of N, N-diglycidyl-furfurylamine (DGFA)

92.8 g (1 mol) epichlorohydrine was heated to 40 °C in a 250 mL three-neck round-bottom flask equipped with magnetic stirring. Then, 48.5 g (0.5 mol) furfural amine was added dropwise. The solution mixture was stirred for 5 h at 60 °C. The reaction solution was cooled to room temperature followed by dropwise addition of 160 ml 50 % (w/v) aqueous sodium hydroxide for over 1 h. The system was held at 30 °C for 5 h. 200 mL ethyl acetate was added, and then the organic layer was collected, washed with water for several times before it was dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate, filtrated, and evaporated to give 80 % liquid. This liquid was further purified by chromatography on a silica gel column using (ethyl acetate/hexane=1/3) as the solvent. Having removed the solvent on a rotary evaporator, a light yellow liquid was obtained at a yield of 50%.

Synthesis of furfuryl glycidyl ether (FGE)

102 g (1.1 mol) epichlorohydrine and 4 g tetrabutylammonium hydrogen sulfate were charged into a 250 mL four-necked round-bottom flask equipped with a stirrer, a

thermometer, and an inlet of dry nitrogen. 98 g (1 mol) furfuryl alcohol was added dropwise while keeping the solution temperature below 25 °C. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h at 25 °C under N₂ atmosphere. After that, 160 ml 50 % (w/v) sodium hydroxide aqueous solution was added dropwise within 30 min. The reaction proceeded for additional 2 h at room temperature. Afterwards, 200 mL ethyl ether was added, and the organic layer was collected, washed with water for several times before it was dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate, filtrated, and evaporated to give 90% liquid. The liquid was further purified by chromatography on a silica gel column using mixed solvent of ethyl acetate/hexane (5/1). The solvent was removed on a rotary evaporator, and lastly, a light yellow liquid was obtained.

Curing of DGFA resin

DGFA resin was cured by a hardener, methylhexahydrophthalic anhydride (MHHPA) at a ratio of epoxy ring/anhydride of 1:0.8. Meanwhile, a stoichiometric ratio of N, N' (4,4'-diphenylmethane) bismaleimide (DPMBMI) was used to react with the furan groups of DGFA. First, DPMBMI was dissolved in DGFA liquid under stirring at 90 °C for 10 min without the help of solvent, and then, MHHPA was mixed with the above mixture at 80 °C for additional 10 min. The resultant homogeneous liquid was degassed, poured into a closed silicone rubber mold and cured at 70 °C for 24 h. Furthermore, a certain amount of FGE was mixed with DGFA resin to adjust the proportion of epoxy and furan groups. Accordingly, the amount of the hardener and bismaleimide was also changed to keep constant ratios of epoxy ring/anhydride and furan/bismaleimide.

Thermal reversibility and remendability assessment of cured DGFA

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed to evaluate the thermal reversibility of DA bonds in the cured DGFA. To assess the remendable behaviour of cured DGFA, a double cleavage drilled compression (DCDC) measure was carried out according to the method reported in ref. [10]. The specimen was a relatively long column of rectangular cross section that contained a through-the-thickness central, circular hole with small notches at its axial crowns. The rectangular column of DCDC specimens had a size of 50×15×8.9 mm³, while the radius of the central hole, R, was 1.98 mm. Having introduced a uniform crack emanating from the upper and lower crowns of the hole, the DCDC samples were quasi-statically loaded in an SANS CMT6000 universal testing machine with displacement control using a 25 kN load cell. Each sample was compressed at a rate of 0.25 μm s⁻¹. Because the sample geometry after healing is macroscopically identical to that before fracturing, the healing efficiency, η, was calculated as a ratio of the stress required to propagate the crack to a given length in the healed material to the stress required to propagate the crack to approximately the same length in the virgin material (Equation 1).

$$\eta = \frac{\sigma_{crit}^{healed}}{\sigma_{crit}^{virgin}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis and characterization of DGFA

The novel epoxy resin, DGFA, was synthesized according to a two-step route (Figure 1). In the first step, ring-opening addition reaction between oxirane ring of epichlorohydrin and amine group of 2-furfurylamine occurred to produce a compound with chlorohydrine end groups. In the second step, DGFA formed through ring-closing reaction of chlorohydrine groups owing to dehydrochlorination action of NaOH solution. After purification by chromatography on a silica gel column, the product of DGFA was characterized with FTIR, $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ and element analysis.

Figure 1 DGFA synthesized by a two-step route.

Figure 2 FTIR spectra of (A) FGE and (B) DGFA.

Oxirane ring of DGFA is present as reflected by the FTIR absorption peaks (Figure 2) at 3051 cm^{-1} (C-H in oxirane ring), 1250 and 851 cm^{-1} (C-O-C), and 918 cm^{-1} (oxirane ring breathing). Furan ring of DGFA is proved by the peaks at 3144 and 3117 cm^{-1} (C-H in furan ring), 1503 cm^{-1} (C=C in furan ring), 1148 cm^{-1} (C-O in furan ring), 1013 cm^{-1}

(furan ring breathing), and 752 cm^{-1} (representing mono-substituted furan ring). Besides, the characteristic peak at 1346 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching vibration of C-N. Similarly, the chemical structure of FGE with one epoxy group and one furan group was also evidenced by FTIR spectrum (Figure 2).

Figure 3 ^1H -NMR spectrum of DGFA

Figure 4 ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of DGFA

In ^1H -NMR spectrum of the reaction product (Figure 3), the peaks at $\delta_{\text{H}} = 3.1\text{--}2.4\text{ ppm}$ are due to the protons designated as “5” in the oxirane rings. Furan ring is identified with the peaks at $\delta_{\text{H}} = 6.2\text{--}6.3\text{ ppm}$ ($=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{}$, 2H) and $\delta_{\text{H}} = 7.3\text{ ppm}$ ($-\text{O}-\text{CH}=\text{C}-$, 1H) corresponding to the protons “2”, “3” and “1”, respectively. The characteristic peak at $\delta_{\text{H}} = 3.8\text{ ppm}$ ($-\text{NCH}_2\text{-furan ring}$, 2H) indicates existence of group “4” that links glycidyl amine to furan ring. Figure 4 shows ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of DGFA with the assignments: 151, 141, 110, 109 (C_{1-4} for furan ring), 66.6, 66.1 (C_5 , $-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{-oxirane}$ ring), 61.1, 60.9 (C_6 , oxirane ring), 60.6 (C_7 , $-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{-furan}$), and 44.8, 44.5 (C_8 , oxirane ring), respectively. Moreover, the result of element analysis also coincides with the chemical structure of DGFA. On the other hand, both ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of FGE provide sufficient evidences for the chemical structure of FGE.

Curing kinetics and mechanical properties of DGFA resin

It is anticipated that the novel epoxy resin, DGFA, should be able to replace the traditional epoxy in wide applications, and prolong service life of the products due to intrinsic remendability. Accordingly, reactivity of the attached epoxide groups in DGFA molecules have to be checked. To understand the curing behavior of DGFA resin, exothermic habit of the model mixture of DGFA and the curing agent methylhexahydrophthalic anhydride (MHHPA) at stoichiometric ratio was inspected with DSC (Figure 5). The corresponding parameters of curing kinetics, like activation energy, E_a , and pre-exponential factor, A , were estimated by Ozawa and Kissinger equations, while reaction order, n , was given by Crane equation (Table 1). It is seen that DGFA can perform curing reaction with MHHPA like conventional epoxy resin, implying that the synthesized DGFA might be applicable for the field in which conventional epoxy resin is employed. The measured activation energy for consolidation of the resin is 36.2 kJ/mol , which is much lower than the value involved

in the similar curing of commercial epoxy resin. In addition, it is found that DGFA can be cured by MHHPA at a temperature as low as ~ 50 °C, which contrasts sharply with the case of conventional epoxy cured by anhydride even in the presence of accelerant (i.e. 100~150 °C). The catalytic effect of the tertiary amine group on DGFA molecules (Figure 6) should take the responsibility.

Figure 5 DSC heating traces of the mixture of DGFA and MHHPA at stoichiometric ratio. Accordingly, non-isothermal curing kinetics can be calculated (see Table 1).

Figure 6 Dependences of characteristic curing temperatures on rate of heating of the mixture of DGFA and MHHPA at stoichiometric ratio. Definitions of T_i , T_p and T_f are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Non-isothermal curing kinetics parameters of DGFA and MHHPA at stoichiometric ratio

ϕ (°C/min)	T_i (°C)	T_p (°C)	T_f (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	Kinetic parameters
2	55	109	209	315	$\ln A = 2.03$ $E_a = 36.2$ kJ/mol $n = 0.84$
5	68	129	224	374	
10	83	159	239	390	
15	96	173	243	370	

ϕ : heating rate.

T_i : onset temperature of the exothermic peak.

T_p : peak exothermic temperature.

T_f : ending temperature of the exothermic peak.

ΔH : heat of reaction.

A : pre-exponential factor.

E_a : activation energy.

n : reaction order.

Tensile and flexural properties of cured DGFA resin were measured at room temperature, in comparison with those of conventional bisphenol-A epoxy cured by MHHPA (Table 2). Cured version of the newly synthesized epoxy has higher modulus

but a moderately lower strength as compared to cured bisphenol-A epoxy [11]. On the whole, the data of the cured DGFA are still close to those of commercial epoxy resins. It means that DGFA possesses potential ability to replace traditional epoxy resin in the future application. A glass transition at around 128 °C was observed by dynamic mechanical measurement for the cured DGFA resin. Moreover, thermal decomposition performance of cured DGFA resin was also estimated. The predominant pyrolysis took place at around 330-390 °C as a result of chain scission of epoxy network. Evidently, the resultant new epoxy has been provided with balanced properties for practical applications.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of cured epoxy

Properties	Cured DGFA resin	Bisphenol-A epoxy cured by MHHPA [11]
Young's modulus (GPa)	2.5	1.8
Tensile strength (MPa)	53	65
Elongation at break (%)	1.5	-
Flexural modulus (GPa)	4.6	2.6
Flexural strength (MPa)	110	128

Thermal reversibility of cured DGFA resin

Since the cured epoxy network consists of two kinds of chemical bonds (i.e. thermally stable crosslinking bonds owing to the reaction of epoxide groups with curing agents, and thermally reversible Diels-Alder bonds), its thermal reversibility should be realized below glass transition temperature. However, thermally reversible reactions may be inhibited by the stable crosslinked epoxy networks. Therefore, thermal reversibility of the cured DGFA polymer should be studied firstly, as it is directly related to thermal remendability of the material.

Reversibility of the cured DGFA resin was monitored by DSC (Figure 7). The retro-DA reaction was carried out by heating the samples at 140 °C for 20 min, while the DA reaction took place at 80 °C for 72 h. The original cured DGFA (DA0) gives an endothermic peak due to retro-DA reaction at 126 °C, while the rDA1 only shows a glass transition at 128.5 °C. This implies that retro-DA reaction has already been completed during the heat treatment at 140 °C for 20 min. Subsequently, the rDA1 is allowed to reconnect the cleavage groups by DA reaction, and then an endothermic peak appears again at 131 °C for DA1. It is evident that DA reaction between the disconnected furan and maleimide moieties has definitely taken place duuring the thermal treatment process. However, the recovery efficiency of the second DA reaction in comparison to the original cured DGFA polymer is about 77 % as given by the ratio of ΔH_1 (enthalpy of DA1) over ΔH_0 (enthalpy of DA0), indicating that the epoxy networks somewhat hinders the recovery of DA bonds. The recyclability of retro-DA and DA reactions in the cured DGFA resin was verified by the repeated endotherms and

T_g transitions for the DA and retro-DA samples up to four times. It is noted that the retro-DA reaction always occurs at a temperature lower than the glass transition temperature of the cured DGFA resin, no matter how many cycles of retro-DA and DA reactions. Thereby, cracks in the cured DGFA epoxy are able to be mended while keeping integrity of the material.

Fig. 11 DSC heating traces of DGFA/MHHPA/DPMBMI crosslinked polymer (heating rate: 5 °C/min). DA0: as-manufactured sample. rDA1: DA0 treated at 140 °C for 20 min, and then quenched to room temperature. DA1: rDA1 treated at 80 °C for 72 h, and then cooled inside oven by switching off electricity supply. rDA2: DA1 treated at 140 °C for 20 min, and then quenched to room temperature. DA2: rDA2 treated at 80 °C for 72 h, and then cooled inside the oven by switching off electricity supply. rDA3: DA2 treated at 140 °C for 20 min, and then quenched to room temperature. DA3: rDA3 treated at 80 °C for 72 h, and then cooled inside the oven by switching off electricity supply.

Thermal remendability of the cured DGFA resin

A particular highlight of the DCDC measure lies in the proposed method allows an accurate estimation of healing performance. Under an increasing uniform axial compression, cracks initiate at the crowns and grow axially in a stable manner, along the mid-plane of the sample. This specimen geometry renders the cracks self-arresting so that the fractured sample remains in one piece after the test, which greatly improves our ability to realign the fracture surfaces prior to healing.

The healing treatment consisted of the following procedure. Following the fracture event (the crack grew to a certain length, l), the sample was immediately placed inside a pre-heated oven at the desired temperature. The healing treatment of the cured epoxy resin with cracks was a two-stage process. The first stage consisted of heating the sample to ~ 120 °C allowing disconnection of the thermally reversible Diels-Alder (DA) bonds (i.e. retro-DA reaction), and then being cooled down to 80 °C enabling recombination of the disconnected linkages (i.e. DA reaction). In this way the epoxy resin was fractured and then mended for consecutive cycles. Table 3 lists the healing efficiencies for the cured DGFA resin and the average healing efficiency, η_{avg} , for each healing cycle. It is noted that the η_{avg} values decrease gradually with fractured and healed cycles, reflecting the hindering effects of epoxy networks. To improve the

healing efficiency, 20 wt.% FGE was mixed with DGFA resin to adjust the proportion of epoxy and furan groups, and then the same DCDC tests were performed. An evident increase in healing efficiency of cured DGFA/FGE 80/20 is showed in Table 4, demonstrating that the healing performance of DGFA resin can be easily adjusted by changing the proportion of thermally stable bonds and thermally reversible bonds.

Table 3 Healing efficiency of cured DGFA resin

<i>Crack length</i>	<i>l/R=1.00</i>		<i>l/R=1.26</i>		<i>l/R=2.14</i>		η_{avg} (%)
	σ_{crit} (MPa)	η (%)	σ_{crit} (MPa)	η (%)	σ_{crit} (MPa)	η (%)	
Virgin	22.5	-	24.4	-	29.1	-	-
Healed-1	14.7	65	16.1	65.8	19.6	67	66
Healed-2	13.7	60	15.27	62.5	18.8	64.6	62.3
Healed-3	13.5	60	14.7	60.2	17.9	60.8	60.3

Table 4 Healing efficiency of cured DGFA/FGE 80/20 resin

<i>Crack length</i>	<i>l/R=1.00</i>		<i>l/R=1.26</i>		<i>l/R=2.14</i>		η_{avg} (%)
	σ_{crit} (MPa)	η (%)	σ_{crit} (MPa)	η (%)	σ_{crit} (MPa)	η (%)	
Virgin	18.9	-	20.5	-	24.5	-	-
Healed	13.6	71	14.8	72	19.5	79	74

CONCLUSIONS

To our knowledge, conventional epoxy does not possess crack remendability. A particular highlight of our work lies in the preparation of a multi-functional or “smart” epoxy material. This type of epoxy not only has mechanica properties like conventional epoxy, but also exhibits thermal remendability. Since the cured epoxy network consists of two kinds of chemical bonds (i.e. thermally stable crosslinking bonds owing to the reaction of epoxide groups with curing agents, and thermally reversible Diels-Alder bonds), its thermal reversibility can be realized below glass transition temperature. Thereby, cracks in the cured epoxy are mended while keeping integrity of the material. Furthermore, by adjusting the proportion of thermally stable bonds and thermally reversible bonds, healing performance of the epoxy can be easily controlled.

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